

IMPORTANCE OF STRESS MANAGEMENT IN PUBLIC SPEAKING

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Abstract

It is assumed that Stress is one of the main factors affecting our life nowadays causing both health problems as well as other losses as a result of not being able to control our emotions, always considering that no one is born a public speaker, we are trained to be so. In the same way no one is excluded from fear, stress and nervousness, we are taught how to overcome it. So, the aim of this paper is to bring some ideas on how to manage stress in our everyday life especially when speaking publically. Some ideas on how to be successful talking to everyone, how to make people think you are important by using your body language like smile, eyes and intellect will be presented in this paper. This paper is based on the research from the outstanding authors of the field like: Stefen Lucas, Shiv KheraLeil Lowndnes, etc. In this paper there will also be mentioned important exercises to avoid stress in public speaking, try to find out what the right outfit is, what techniques to use and many other aspects which will help one perform well in public. The purpose of this paper is also to analyze the of stress level and nervousness in university students while speaking in class as it is considered the first public place for them and recommend strategies to overcome this so called speaking stress. Questionnaires will be used with both teachers, directors, and public speakers of different fields as well as with students of the University Fehmi Agani in Gjakova to better analyze stress level of respondents as well as to get the best recommendations on how to avoid it. Based on this the following Research questions will be answered in order to come to the Hypothesis:

- How much does the stress on students and employees impacts the public speaking?
- Does the stress management increase the performance in public speaking?

Keywords: Stress, nervousness, fear, public speaking, management, skills

1. INTRODUCTION

It is assumed that Stress is one of the main factors nowadays affecting our life causing both health problems as well as other losses as a result of not being able to control our emotions. Everyday starting from the early morning when we open our eyes we start thinking about the tests, homework, home tasks, traffic jam, workload of the day, about the task awaiting to be performed and many other thinks going on into our brain making our day harder and busier. As soon as we meet the first person we hear the word Stress, we hear it from our colleagues, teachers, family members and friends. We hear it even in the media as it has become a daily routine as our life has changed from the past requiring more combination of time and energy. If you do not use it rationally it goes away. Busy life requires more compulsion of thoughts and emotions as our life instrument is time consuming in relation to our duties. So stress affects our mood, energy level, relationships, work performance etc.

The purpose of this paper is also to analyze the reasons behind the stress level and nervousness during public speaking in people of different professions whose job is to speak publically in daily or weekly bases as well as in undergraduate students (including master and PhD-s too) when speaking in class and other public places and recommend strategies to overcome this fear.

Questionnaires will be used with both teachers, directors, and public speakers of different fields as well as with students of the University “Fehmi Agani” in Gjakova to better analyze stress level of respondents as well as to get the best recommendations on how to avoid it.

The structure of this paper is as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature from outstanding authors and stress coaches of the field discussed in this study. Section 3 analyses the research methodology that has been used to conduct empirical research. Section 4 presents the results of the study, including the analysis of the data and the results obtained from the relevant analyses. Section 5 provides conclusions reached based on the findings of the paper.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Let us first understand what stress is. According to medicine stress is body's response to physical, mental, or emotional pressure, causing chemical changes in the body that can raise blood pressure, heart rate, and blood sugar levels. It may also lead to feelings of frustration, anxiety, anger, or depression. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/> writes that “Stress is our built-in response to danger, a surge in hormones as we choose between fighting, fleeing, or freezing. This danger may be real or imagined, immediate or farther away; our bodies don't know the difference”. Considering that no one is excluded from fear, stress and nervousness and that we are taught how to overcome it, I would consider Sadhguru (2018) saying that “No work is stressful. It is our inability to manage our Body, Mind and Emotions that make it stressful: So, according to Sadhguru “understanding stress can help one know more quickly when help is needed, understand what helps best or what works the best.”

Second important thing to understand is the stress management, how to best keep our emotions and hormones under control.

“We don't have absolute choice to choose our situations, but we have been given the freedom to choose our experience.” – Sadhguru. We have to find the best ways to keep things under control.

Stress management mainly means changing our life, by taking more care of ourselves by taking things easier when stressful situations occur in life because not all stress is bad. When in stress we should just believe in ourselves and our values and suddenly our mind will be released because as Shiv Khera (2019) said, “distorted values lead to tragedy” the same as the fear of failure by thinking, “What if I don't make it?” Positive thoughts bring success, believe in yourself and you will achieve what you want. Negative self-talk or negative auto-suggestions according to Shiv Khera only reinforce the negative by conditioning the subconscious mind adversely and pull us down. Negative statements like; I am not good in performing my duties, or I will fail, etc. makes our mind believe and our behavior change accordingly. These become

a self-fulfilling prophecies. Successful people realize their limitations but focus on their strengths. (Shiv Khera 2019).

Different authors give different opinions on stress. Amond (1960) says that “stress is any condition that disturbs normal functioning”, while according to Beehr & Newman (1978) “stress is a condition arising from the interaction between people and their jobs characterized by changes within people that force them to deviate from their normal functioning”.

On the other side based on Selye (1974) “Stress is a non-specific response of the body to certain demand”.

As this paper concentrates on stress in public speaking it is mandatory to discuss what is included in public speaking or as it is known as Oratory which traditionally has meant any live or direct speaking face to face to a larger audience. But today it includes” any formal or informal speaking to an audience included pre-recorded speech delivered or spread over a distance by means of the technology.” It means that a public speaker can be any person speaking to a group of people is it live or recorded in advance and transmitted through media, TV, radio, videoconference, multimedia conferences or other forms of information. It includes, company leaders, teachers, students, etc. It includes anyone who has an excellent communication skills enthusiasm and ability to engage with an audience, anyone who is able to transfer itself into public, be a part of public. Always a group is larger and better than an individual so, in public speaking it is important to use the first person plural “WE” instead of “I”.

Based on work by Buss (1980) and Motley (1991), three sources of anxiety were identified:” the degree of formal evaluation, level of audience interest in the topic, and the audience's responsiveness to the speaker.” In addition to public speaking anxiety, measures were taken of willingness to speak and expected speech quality. “Interest, responsiveness, and formal evaluation showed effects on all of the anxiety-related variables.”

The best stress management techniques before speaking:

- Practise your speech.
- Relax Your Muscles.
- Take a deep breath and keep you head up
- Keep the public under control by looking them in the eyes
- Speak slowly and be confident
- Take a Break time after time.

Perhaps Skills required to be a public speaker (Peter Khory) are:

You have to connect yourself with the topic and then connect your topic with the audience.

This concept is called the “Triangle of Trust” in the speaking world. When you do it right, the audience will love, trust, and follow you. When you do it the wrong way, the audience will mistrust you.

If you talk about yourself without connecting to the topic, then your introduction will be out of context. People will wonder why you are talking about this particular subject.

If you talk about yourself without connecting to the audience, then no one will care. People do not like to listen to others when they do not feel any emotional connection to the other person.

1: “ Triangle of Trust” by Peter Khoury The New York Times (2016)

3. METHODOLOGY

In order to answer all these above mentioned questions and many others questionnaires are used with both teachers, directors, and public speakers of different fields as well as with students of the University Fehmi Agani in Gjakova to better analyze stress level of respondents as well as to get the best recommendations on how to avoid it.

The questionnaire contains 23 open and close ended questions and comments at the end of it given by each respondent. The research was done in those institutions that are claimed to have public speaking I their daily program.

Based on this the following **Research questions** will be answered in order to come to the Hypothesis:

1. How much does the stress on students and employees impacts the public speaking?
2. Does the stress management increase the performance in public speaking?

HYPOTHESES

Hypothesis H0: The stress of students and employees has no impact on public speaking.

Hypothesis H1: The stress of students and employees has an impact on public speaking.

Hypothesis H3: The proper stress management increases the performance of communication with the public.

4. ANALYSIS OF MULTIPLE STANDARD REGRESSION

The research issues elaborated in the presentation of results and their discussion are oriented and derived from these hypotheses:

Hypothesis H₀: **The stress of students and employees has no impact on public speaking.**

Hypothesis H₁: **The stress of students and employees has an impact on public speaking.**

Hypothesis H₃: **The proper stress management increases the performance of communication with the public.**

Model Summary				
<p>Model summary shows the R value for evaluating the suitability of the model. This model shows how well the independent variable explains the dependent variable, where in our case R² has emerged 0.857 x 100 = 85.7%. This means that independent variables in the regression explain in the extent dependent variable: The impact of stress on students and employees in public speaking.</p>				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.906 ^a	.857	.857	.226
a. Predictors: (Constant) personality, motivation, communication, character, stimulation				

Coefficients ^{a-}						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.458	.194		2.067	.002
	Personality	.135	.110	.247	2.987	.001
	Motivation	.360	.095	.432	3.427	.000
	Communication	.534	.124	.742	4.305	.000
	Character	.837	.082	.943	6.177	.003
	Stimulation	.419	.159	.348	4.629	.001
a. Dependent Variable: The impact of stress on students and employees in public speaking						

Based on the results in the table we see that the independent variables: personality, motivation, communication, character, stimulation are at a lower significance level of less than 5% that means have statistical and economic significance in the dependent variable. Based on these data we can say that H₀ is rejected and H₁ stands or is accepted. The interpretation for hypotheses H₁ is: **The stress of students and employees has an impact on public speaking.**

Correlations			
		Stress management	The performance on public speaking
Stress management	Pearson Correlation	1	.899**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
The performance on public speaking	Pearson Correlation	.899**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			
** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).			

In the table above is shown correlation coefficient that gives us a mathematical value to measure the linear power between the two interconnected variables. The table shows two variables that are closely related to each other. Both of these variables are at a significance level of 0.000, which is less than 5% which means they have a positive relation. The research question: **Does stress management affect performance growth in public speaking?** Based on the results in the tables we can say that: **The proper stress management increases the performance of communication with the public.**

5. CONCLUSION

In this article it was tried hard to bring some ideas on how to manage stress in our everyday life especially when speaking publically. Some ideas on how to be successful talking to everyone, how to make people think you are important by using your body language like smile, eyes and intellect were discussed. Books from many outstanding authors of the field are discussed like: Stefen Lucas. Shiv Khera, LeilLowndnes, James Williams, etc.

In this paper there are also mentioned important exercises to avoid stress in public speaking, it was tried to find out what the right outfit is, what techniques to use and many other aspects which will help one perform well in public. The purpose of this paper was also to analyze the reasons of stress level and nervousness in university students when speaking in class as it is considered the first public speaking place for them some strategies to overcome this kind of stress are presented.

Our research concluded among others that in order to be successful speaker and speak fearlessly one should link the topic and the audience to itself as If you talk about yourself without connecting to the audience, then no one will care. People do not like to listen to others when they do not feel any emotional connection to the other person. This done by being confident, speaking slowly, keeping head up and looking the audience in the eyes. Eye contact plays the main role.

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